

PERCEiVE

Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collEctions
through al and Virtual Experiences

a cultural
probe kit
on authenticity

activity book and diary

for designers to explore and
develop authentic experiences in
Digital Heritage

This work is part of a research project conducted by CNR ISPC and the University of Bologna – DHDK (Interactive Media Design course). It has been further developed within the PERCEIVE project to explore and study “Authenticity” and its triggers in XR experiences.

PERCEIVE, Perceptive enhanced realities of colored collections through AI and virtual experiences (Grant Agreement N. 101061157) has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program, <http://www.perceive-horizon.eu>

The authors agree to enable scholars to use it free of charge, quoting it as:

Spotti S., Pescarin S. (2023). “Cultural Probe Kit on Authenticity triggers in XR experiences: activity book and diary for designers to explore and develop authentic experiences in Digital Heritage”. 2023

Edition: 1st Edition – 2023

Digital Publication: 25 August 2023

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8286449

Pages 43

Subjects: Interactive Media Design, Museum and Heritage Studies

Table of content

Instructions	9
1: my Activity Book	10
2: my Diary	20
3: my Activity Book	
Authenticity Stories	33

My Cultural Probe Kit

Number __

Dear Friend, this is a kit made for you. It is called “Cultural Probe Kit” because it is used by designers to explore cultural behaviours and needs of their audience, in the creation of digital applications.

This particular Kit is meant to investigate how Authenticity and its dimensions and how they could be used by Interactive Media.

It will be with you for the next 15 days. Please take care of it. It is composed by three parts.

We are a team of researchers of the National Research Council Institute of Heritage Science, CNR ISPC, and CNR ITD, and master students of DHDK at the University of Bologna.

Your contribution is anonymous; we ask you to NOT add your name and to SIGN here below, that you have read and agree with the instructions and with the potential use of the results for scientific publications, without any reference to personal indications.

Date

Signature

Instructions

This notebook is composed by 3 sections:

In the first, you'll be asked to complete daily tasks; In the second, you'll find a diary that will be with you for 8 days; the last contains more advanced tasks related to Cultural Heritage.

You won't need any previous experience nor particular technology, just a pen, your phone (to scan QRcodes and access online material), and some of your time.

Please fill this book in complete sincerity, it will be completely anonymous and you will not be judged for your answers.

When you have finished, please take pictures of every page and send them to this e-mail: samuele.spotti@ispc.cnr.it. Or you can **upload them** at this link:

<https://forms.gle/CkMzCh9DoDt58WSF7> or scan the QRcode to access it.

You have 15 days to finish all activities

My Cultural Probe Kit

1: my Activity Book

Activity 1

Who am I?

Please Include here the number of your kit: _____

Year of Birth* _____

Nationality* _____

What is your last degree? (i.e. undergraduate, graduate, master, phd, etc.)*

In which field you took your last degree? (i.e. Humanities, Economics, etc.)

How often do you visit sites or Monuments?*

Never 1 2 3 4 5 Often

How often do you visit museums?*

Never 1 2 3 4 5 Often

How often do you visit temporary exhibitions?*

Never 1 2 3 4 5 Often

With whom do you visit sites or museums? *

- Alone Friends Colleagues Family School
 Strangers in guided visits Other: _____

Activity 2

Authenticity perception in your experiences

This activity is part of an on-going research activity carried out by the Institute of Heritage Science of the Italian Research Council (CNR ISPC) and by the University of Bologna (Master DHDK). It is also part of a Cultural Probe Kit that is used to help Interactive Media Design.

Frame this QRcode with your phone and follow the link to complete the activities.

Scan the Qrcode to complete via a Google Doc all the questions in Part 1 (Tasks 1-7). You can also read the tasks in this book. The Google Doc is created to host your pictures, videos, thoughts and feelings regarding the perception of authenticity in your visit at Palazzo Poggi Museum.

Activity 3

You are going to visit one of the Museums of your city today.

This is my museum

This activity is meant to make you reflect on **authenticity perception in your experience.**

During the visit: Take a photo of something you experienced as AUTHENTIC (photo or video). don't think about something realistic or real, you should consider what you perceive as "authentic".

Upload your photo here and reply (max 100 Mb)

QRCODE

What are the elements in this photo that you have perceived as AUTHENTIC and why?

Activity 4

Take a photo of something you experienced as NON-AUTHENTIC (photo or video) and upload it here and reply (max 100 Mb).

Please, don't think about something unrealistic, you should consider what you perceived as "non-authentic".

Without these elements, would the experience change? Why?

If you replied "NO". What would you add to increase the degree of authenticity?

Activity 5

Reflecting on the museum visit...

Why was this experience authentic?

Activity 6

Could it be "untruthful"?

- Yes
- No
- Other

If you replied "NO". what would you add to
increase the degree of authenticity?

Activity 7

Being alone or with a group, does it impact the perception of authenticity of the experience?

and why

Do you think that authenticity depends on? You can choose more than one

- Expectations
- Stereotypes
- Traditions
- Knowledge/know how
- Other

Thanks for your contribution!

Now that you have finished, you can take the Activity Book back to the researcher or assistant who gave it to you, or you can keep it, if you like.

In this case, we ask you to take pictures or scan every page and upload them at this link [<https://forms.gle/CkMzCh9DoDt58WSF7>] or scan the QRcode to access the link and upload it.

My Cultural Probe Kit

2: my Diary

Number ____

Starting Date _____

Dear Friend, this little diary will be with you for the next 8 days. Please take care of it. It is the second part of you “cultural probe kit”. It is used by designers to explore behaviours and needs of their audience.

It will be a way also for you to reflect on your life and on concepts such as “authenticity” and on the role of interactive technologies.

We are a team of researchers of the National Research Council Institute of Heritage Science (CNR ISPC), and a group of students of the master DHDK at the University of Bologna.

Your contribution will be anonymous; we ask you to NOT add your name and to sign that you have read and agree with the instructions and with the potential use of the results for scientific publications, without any reference to personal indications.

Date

Signature

Diary Instructions

This diary is the second part of your Cultural Probe Kit. You are going to fill in and complete it after part one (Activity Book). It is going to help you in focusing and reflecting. Every day, possibly before going to sleep, you are invited to think about your day, following suggestions about social cohesion. Write everything sincerely, in these pages. Your diary is anonymous, and we will respect your ideas and privacy.

You have 8 days to complete the diary

When you have finished, you can take it back to the researcher or assistant who gave it to you, or you can keep it, if you like. In this case we ask you to take pictures or scan every page and send it to samuele.spotti@ispc.cnr.it

Date: _____

DAY 1

Today I lived an experience I could define
Authentic: This is what happened

I thought it was authentic because

What made really authentic this experience was:

A: ; B: ; C:

I could rate its authenticity:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

It made me feel:

Date: _____

DAY 2

Today I lived an experience I could define
Authentic: This is what happened

I thought it was authentic because

What made really authentic this experience was:

A: ; B: ; C:

I could rate its authenticity:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

It made me feel:

Date: _____

DAY 3

Today I lived an experience I could define
Authentic: This is what happened

I thought it was authentic because

What made really authentic this experience was:

A: ; B: ; C: ;

I could rate its authenticity:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

It made me feel:

Date: _____

DAY 4

Today I lived an experience I could define

Authentic: This is what happened

I thought it was authentic because

What made really authentic this experience was:

A: ; B: ; C:

I could rate its authenticity:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

It made me feel:

Date: _____

DAY 5

Today I lived an experience I could define
Authentic: This is what happened

I thought it was authentic because

What made really authentic this experience was:

A: ; B: ; C:

I could rate its authenticity:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

It made me feel:

Date: _____

DAY 6

Today I lived an experience I could define
Authentic: This is what happened

I thought it was authentic because

What made really authentic this experience was:

A: ; B: ; C: ;

I could rate its authenticity:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

It made me feel:

Date: _____

DAY 7

Today I lived an experience I could define
Authentic: This is what happened

I thought it was authentic because

What made really authentic this experience was:

A: ; B: ; C: ;

I could rate its authenticity:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

It made me feel:

Date: _____

DAY 8

Today I lived an experience I could define
Authentic: This is what happened

I thought it was authentic because

What made really authentic this experience was:

A: ; B: ; C:

I could rate its authenticity:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

It made me feel:

Thanks for your contribution!

Now that you have finished, you can take the diary back to the researcher or assistant who gave it to you, or you can keep it, if you like.

In this case, we ask you to take pictures or scan every page and send it to samuele.spotti@ispc.cnr.it

My Cultural Probe Kit

3: my Activity Book

Authenticity Stories

Number ____

Activity 8

Authentic Experiences and Authenticity Perception

This space is here to host your thoughts and feelings regarding the PERCEPTION OF AUTHENTICITY. This activity is part of an on-going research activity carried out by the Institute of Heritage Science of the Italian Research Council (CNR ISPC) and by the University of Bologna (Master DHDK). It is also part of a Cultural Probe Kit that is used to help Interactive Media Design.

Please read the initial suggestion and feel free to write your stories and your life episodes, that would be treated anonymously (we will not know your name) and shared ONLY if you allow us to do so.

Your email will be used to send your stories back to you.

Frame this QRcode with your phone and follow the link to complete the activities.

Scan the Qrcode to complete via a Google Doc all the questions in this Part. You can also read the tasks in this book. The Google Doc is created to host your pictures, videos, thoughts and feelings regarding the perception of authenticity in your life.

Activity 9

Write a story about an experience you had in your life, in which you felt it was absolutely authentic.

It should not be "real" or "realistic", but "authentic". Take some time and write the story on paper or in your text editor (yes it would have been easier to write it directly here, but we noticed that it's easier to take some time in this way).

When you have done take a picture of the paper or upload the PDF or Word file

My Story about an authentic experience

You can share also a picture of that experience
(maximum 10 Mb)

Activity 10

Read your story again and reflect

In the story you just wrote, what have been the elements that made really authentic the experience?

Which basic emotions characterized that experience, making it so authentic. You can choose more than one:

- Fear
- Happiness
- Sadness
- Disgust
- Anger
- Surprise

What senses were mostly involved in the perception of authenticity?

- Sight / visual elements
- Hearing / sounds
- Touch
- Sense of Smell
- Taste

What other aspects you would see as indicators of authenticity in that experience? You can choose more than one.

- Emotional impact
- Presence of other people
- Exchange of thoughts/ideas etc. with other people
- Unicity / Peculiarity
- Unpredictability of what happened
- Immediate Feedback / Real time reply
- Action (the fact that I could do something)
- Other

Activity 11

Read the diary and reflect

This activity is aimed to explore what, why and how we perceive an experience, also in VR, as authentic and to better understand how technologies could help in strengthening the perception of authenticity.

Frame this QRcode with your phone and follow the link to complete the activities on line. You can also read and complete here.

Look back at your diary. Do you think that your perception of authenticity could be connected with emotions?

Yes No

Which emotion you think is more connected to authentic experiences, in the diary?

Activity 12

Modigliani VR: watch and reply

Watch the video “Modigliani VR at the Tate Gallery”. This video shows the walkthrough of an immersive 3d experience created by the Tate Gallery in London, during the exhibition on Modigliani, the painter: [Modigliani VR \(2020\)](#)

Watch also the “behind the scene” video: What's behind Modigliani VR experience? [The Making of Modigliani VR: The Ochre Atelier](#)

Authenticity and reliability. Think about a virtual experience created by a credible, trustworthy institution, such as the Tate Gallery. Do you think such "reliability" can make the digital experience more authentic? and Why?

Now Describe the digital experience YOU had in your life you found the most authentic. Could you describe it? Why was it authentic for you?

Activity 13

Matrix Awakens: watch and reply

Watch this video: Unreal 5 with Matrix spot.

[The Matrix Awakens: An Unreal Engine 5 Experience](#)

Could you define the experience of the video (Unreal Engine 5 Spot) "authentic"?

Yes No Other _____

Consider what you have written in the diary. Were there elements / indicators of authenticity that you find here in the video? Is there something new?

Can you compare this video with other digital experiences you find to be the most authentic? Could you make some examples?

Thanks for your contribution!

Now that you have finished, you can take the Activity Book back to the researcher or assistant who gave it to you, or you can keep it, if you like.

In this case, we ask you to take pictures or scan every page and upload them at this link [<https://forms.gle/CkMzCh9DoDt58WSF7>] or scan the QRcode to access the link and upload it.

Quote this publication as:

Spotti S., Pescarin S. (2023). “Cultural Probe Kit on Authenticity triggers in XR experiences: activity book and diary for designers to explore and develop authentic experiences in Digital Heritage”

2023

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8286449